

A Gravitational Search Algorithm for Solving the Relay Node Placement Problem in Wireless Sensor Networks

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SUMMARY

Nowadays, the use of Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) is increasing in many fields of application, such as industrial monitoring, home automation, and intensive agriculture. However, this technology presents an important shortcoming, which has not been solved yet: the energy-efficiency. This factor involves a critical economic disadvantage, affecting Quality of Service (QoS). This situation led us to tackle the Relay Node Placement Problem (RNPP), i.e. the addition of relay nodes to traditional WSNs as a way to optimize such networks, assuming two important factors: energy consumption and average coverage. To achieve this goal, three MultiObjective (MO) evolutionary algorithms are considered (NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-GSA), assuming a freely available data set and different stop criteria to analyze the behavior of the algorithms. All the results obtained are studied through a widely accepted statistical methodology and two MO metrics (hypervolume and set coverage), concluding that the novel swarm intelligence algorithm MO-GSA provides the best performance on average. Moreover, we study the advantages provided by the addition of relay nodes to traditional WSNs. Finally, we compare our proposal to another author approach, assuming a heuristic. Copyright © xxxx John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.

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KEY WORDS: wireless sensor network; quality of service; multiobjective optimization; relay node deployment; evolutionary computation; swarm intelligence

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) has increased substantially in recent years. Usually, a traditional WSN consists of a set of sensors and a collector node. The sensors measure physical variables about the environment, which are sent to the collector node. The sensors have some features, which encourage the use of WSNs, such as they are small, low-cost, wireless, and able to collect different types of measures in a same device. These factors, among others, allow considering WSNs in environments, where the deployment of other technologies would be very expensive or impossible. In this line, there are many applications for WSNs in both civil (industrial control, security, home automation, intensive agriculture) and military (rescue operations, surveillance) areas [1, 2]. However, WSNs also have important shortcomings, affecting Quality of Service (QoS), i.e. maintenance and deployment costs, reliability, coverage, and power consumption, among others.

Traditionally, the sensors are powered by batteries to avoid the use of wires, reducing deployment costs. The batteries limit the network lifetime and imply an obvious power consumption dependence. Each time a sensor captures data, the device has to send it to the collector node, following some routing protocol. In a star topology, all the devices have a similar energy cost.

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However, if we consider a habitual multi-hop communication model, the sensors are subject to unbalanced energy costs, involving the existence of bottlenecks and affecting the network behavior.

With the objective of alleviating this issue, a new device called relay node is added to such networks. These new devices only forward all the received information to the collector node, so reducing the workload of the sensors in communication tasks [3, 4]. The efficient deployment of these devices is known as the Relay Node Placement Problem (RNPP) in the literature.

The efficient deployment of WSNs depends on many factors, even more if relay nodes are added. This problem was defined as an NP-hard optimization problem [5] in the literature [6, 7]. Hence, it cannot be solved through exact techniques, but considering non-conventional or approximate methodologies, such as heuristics, linear programming, and Evolutionary Computation (EC). In this paper, we study how to deploy relay nodes in previously-established static traditional WSNs in order to simultaneously optimize two relevant factors by considering EC, because this set of techniques provides good approximate solutions solving such optimization problems [8].

We make the following contributions in this work:

- Three MultiObjective (MO) algorithms from EC are considered to solve this NP-hard MO optimization problem. Two of them, NSGA-II [9] and SPEA2 [10], are well-known Genetic Algorithms (GAs) and the remainder (an MO version of GSA [11]) is a memetic algorithm based on the Newtonian gravity and motion laws, which was not previously assumed for this purpose. Both NSGA-II and SPEA2 were assumed to this end in two early papers [12, 13].
- We consider two relevant factors for the industry, which negatively affect QoS: average energy cost of the sensors and average coverage provided by the network, influencing maintenance costs, because of battery replacement and the amount of information captured, respectively.
- Comparing to other methodologies, such as heuristics or linear programming, our approach provides a set of candidate solutions to the RNPP. Thus, the network designer gets a trade-off between both factors, selecting the most favorable solution for a specific case.
- Two MO metrics are assumed to analyze the quality of the results obtained: hypervolume [14] and set coverage [8], considering a widely accepted statistical methodology.
- Most papers in the literature assume non-public or randomly generated data sets. In this work, we consider a freely available data set [15]. This means that our proposal could be replicated and enhanced by other authors in future works.
- We study the advantages, which accrue from deploying relay nodes in traditional WSNs. Moreover, we include a comparative study between our proposal and another author approach.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. The literature review is discussed in Section 2. Next, the problem formulation appears in Section 3. Some relevant aspects of EC are exposed in Section 4. The MO metaheuristics are explained in Section 5. The experimental results are discussed in Section 6, followed by the comparisons to other author approaches in Section 7. Finally, conclusions and future works are presented in Section 8.

2. RELATED WORK

Two main lines of research stand out for WSN deployment: works studying the deployment of traditional WSNs and works including relay nodes as a way to optimize them [16].

Taking the first approach, we may cite some relevant contributions assuming heuristics. Cheng et al. [6] optimized the energy cost by assigning different power transmission levels to the sensors. Chang and Tassiulas [17] optimized the routing protocol to increase the network lifetime. Cardei and Du [18] optimized the network lifetime by splitting the WSN in disjoint sets of sensors, deciding which had to be active at each time. Zhang and Hou [19] optimized connectivity and sensing coverage by keeping a minimum number of sensors in the active mode. Liu et al. [20] optimized the network lifetime by splitting the WSN as did Cardei and Du [18], while maintaining coverage and connectivity. Mahboubi et al. [21] developed sensor deployment strategies based on Voronoi polygons, with the purpose of increasing coverage in wireless mobile sensor networks.

Other authors considered EC for the same purpose. Konstantinidis et al. [22] assumed a MultiObjective Evolutionary Algorithm (MOEA) based on decomposition in order to increase coverage and network lifetime. Jia et al. [23] applied an MO GA to split the network in disjoint sets of sensors, optimizing coverage and the size of the sets. Jia et al. [24] assumed sensors with adjustable sensing radius and NSGA-II for the same purpose as in [23]. Hou et al. [25] maximized the network lifetime through a GA, splitting the WSN as in [18]. Konstantinidis and Yang [26] enhanced [22] by ensuring a certain connectivity. Le Berre et al. [27] optimized lifetime, coverage, and financial cost by applying several MOEAs. Martins et al. [28] applied an MO hybrid algorithm for performing density control, increasing the network lifetime. Yoon et al. [29] developed a GA to deploy sensors by maximizing the network coverage. Mini et al. [30] proposed a two-step algorithm. Firstly, they deployed the sensor nodes at optimal locations, such that the theoretically computed network lifetime was maximum. Secondly, they scheduled the sensors by a swarm intelligence algorithm, such that the network attained the maximum lifetime.

Most papers taking the first approach show a high dependence of the energy-efficiency, i.e. the sensors close to the collector node are subject to unbalanced energy costs, involving bottlenecks and affecting the network behavior. For this reason, this type of network traditionally assumes a high number of redundant sensors to increase the network lifetime. This means high deployment and maintenance costs. As a possible solution to this issue, the addition of relay nodes could be a good alternative to deploy energy-efficient WSNs without using redundant sensors. Following this second line of research, we find two different approaches: single-tiered and two-tiered networks. In the first one, all the devices can communicate among them, assuming multi-hop routing. The second one is a cluster-based approach, where the sensors send the data to the cluster-head (a relay node) in one hop, and then the cluster-heads forward the information to the collector node in one or more hops.

Taking the second line of research, several authors also considered heuristics. Hou et al. [31] prolonged the network lifetime and mitigated network geometric deficiencies in two-tiered WSNs. Tang et al. [32] presented two polynomial time approximation algorithms to deploy the minimum number of relay nodes in two-tiered WSNs, ensuring connectivity and fault-tolerance. Wang et al. [33] minimized the network cost in two-tiered WSNs with constraints on lifetime and connectivity, describing two models: relay nodes were not energy constrained and all the nodes were energy limited. Lloyd and Xue [34] optimized the network lifetime and preserved network connectivity in single-tiered WSNs by two approaches: between each pair of sensors there was a connecting path consisting of relay and/or sensor nodes, and on the other hand, the path was only composed of relay nodes. Han et al. [35] deployed relay nodes to provide fault-tolerance in single-tiered WSNs, considering sensors with different transmission radius. Xu et al. [3] studied the impacts of random device placement on connectivity and lifetime in two-tiered WSNs. Misra et al. [36] placed a minimum number of relay nodes in single-tiered WSNs to ensure connectivity, where the devices were constrained to be placed at a subset of candidate locations. Misra et al. [37] studied the constrained RNPP in an energy-harvesting single-tiered network, in which the energy-harvesting potential of the candidate locations was known a priori, the objective was to place a minimum number of relay nodes in order to achieve connectivity and survivability. Nigam et al. [38] formulated a branch-and-cut algorithm, with the purpose of placing the minimum number of relay nodes at a subset of candidate locations in single-tiered WSNs, in such a manner that signals from the sensors were communicated to the collector within a prespecified delay bound.

Following this line, several authors considered EC. Zhao and Chen [39] applied a particle swarm algorithm to obtain the optimal energy-efficiency by minimizing the average path length in single-tiered WSNs. Perez et al. [40] formulated an MO model to optimize both the number of relay nodes and the energy dissipation in constrained single-tiered WSNs. Peiravi et al. [41] presented a method of clustering homogeneous two-tiered WSNs using an MO two-nested GA, with the goal of obtaining clustering schemes, where the network lifetime was optimized for different delay values.

Our proposal differs from the existing works described above in the following: i) we consider a single-tiered approach of the RNPP. This type of network is habitually assumed in medium-size networks, where devices are low-cost. Thus, the relay nodes are similar to the sensors, but they do not have circuits for capturing data, having additional energy capacity, e.g. greater batteries or solar

Figure 1. WSN model considered.

panels. ii) we consider an unconstrained approach of the problem. Hence, the relay nodes can be placed in anywhere of the surface. There are applications, such as intensive agriculture, where this situation is desirable. Thus, the search space is greater. iii) we assume EC in order to get a trade-off between the objective functions, having the network designer several possibilities. As described before, there are many works assuming heuristics for single-tiered WSNs [34, 35, 36, 37, 38]. However, this is not the case for EC [39, 40]. Our work differs from these in the following: in [39], the authors assumed a singleobjective problem, but our approach is an MO problem. In [40], they considered a constrained MO RNPP; however, our work assumes an unconstrained MO RNPP.

This way, we consider three MO metaheuristics to tackle an unconstrained version of the RNPP for single-tiered WSNs. We started this work with an important limitation: we did not find any similar paper providing a free-access data set for experimental purposes. Most of them assumed randomly generated data set or non-public ones. In this work, we provide a free-access data set, allowing other researchers to replicate and enhance our proposal. This data set was optimized by the algorithms previously cited, checking as our methodology provides a good behavior.

This work is partially inspired by two very early papers [12, 13], where we assumed NSGA-II and SPEA2 for the same purpose. Now, we present a more complete approach, including a novel swarm intelligence algorithm, a more complete problem definition, two different MO metrics, a comparison to another author approach, and additional comparative studies.

3. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We consider a WSN placed on a 2D-surface of size $D_x \times D_y$, which is composed of M sensors, N relay nodes, and a collector node (Fig. 1). The relay nodes are similar to the sensors, but they do not have circuits for capturing data, having more energy capacity than the sensors. This way, the relay nodes could be powered by greater batteries, be plugged into the grid, or be energy-harvesting devices. In this case, we assume that the relay nodes are energy-harvesting. Consequently, they are not limited to be deployed close to a plug and they do not have shortcomings related to battery charge. The collector node is plugged into the grid, because of the high workload.

A simplified unit disk communication model is assumed. Thus, any two devices are linked if they are at a distance lower than the communication radius R_c , i.e. transmissions within this range are perfectly received and outside this range they are not received at all.

At regular basis and simultaneously, the sensors capture information about the environment with a sensitivity radius R_s . Each time a sensor captures an information packet of K bytes, the measure is sent to the collector node, assuming a multi-hop routing protocol provided by Dijkstra's algorithm [42] for minimum path among devices. Finally, the relay nodes forward all the information received to the collector node, so reducing the workload of the sensors in communication tasks.

The energy model proposed in [22] is considered to simulate the energy expenditure suffered by the sensors. This model incorporates a packet loss mechanism to generate additional energy cost due to retransmissions, with the purpose of complementing the unit disk communication model, getting a more realistic approach. In addition, we consider both a perfect synchronization among all the devices and a MAC protocol, such as S-MAC [43], which is successful in putting the radio of a node into sleep mode under several conditions, e.g. if it is not the transmitter or the receiver of a packet. Thus, all the sensor nodes sleep and wake up at the same time, saving energy.

As this model defines, the transmission power that a sensor $i \in 1, 2 \dots M$ needs to reach any other device $j \in 1, 2 \dots M + N + 1$ is given by

$$P_i = \beta \cdot d_{i,j}^\alpha / d_{i,j} < R_c, \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha \in [2, 6]$ is the path loss exponent, $\beta > 0$ is the transmission quality parameter, and $d_{i,j}$ is the Euclidean distance between i and j . Initially, all the sensors have the same initial energy charge IEC , which will be decreased so long as the sensors send packets. This way, the residual energy of a sensor i at time $t > 0$ is defined as

$$E_i(t) = E_i(t-1) - [(r_i(t) + 1) \cdot P_i \cdot amp \cdot K], \quad (2)$$

where $r_i(t)$ is the number of incoming packets, which i receives from other devices and has to forward to the collector node, the $+1$ term is because the packet generated by i at this time, K is the information packet size, and amp is the energy consumption per bit of the power amplifier. The energy consumption in the receiving, processing, and sensing tasks is considered negligible.

The network lifetime is an important concept in WSNs. It is the number of time units, over which a WSN provides useful information about the environment. To this end, a coverage threshold CV is usually assumed. This way, if the coverage provided by the network is lower than CV , we assume that the amount of information is not enough. Note that if a sensor is out of energy, the coverage provided by such sensor is not considered.

This way, we define an NP-hard MO optimization problem given the number of sensors (M) and their coordinates, the scenario dimension ($D_x \times D_y$), the position of the collector node (C), both the communication and sensitivity radius (R_c and R_s), the initial energy charge of the sensors (IEC), the information packet size (K), the energy consumption per bit of the power amplifier (amp), the transmission quality parameter (β), the path loss exponent (α), the coverage threshold (CV), and the number of relay nodes (N), which we want to deploy. Given these parameters, the objective is to obtain the coordinates of the N relay nodes, which optimize the following fitness functions:

- Average Energy Consumption (AEC , to minimize): Average energy consumption of the sensors over the network lifetime, in Joules (J). The fitness function is defined as

$$f_1 = LF_{cv}^{-1} \cdot \sum_{t=1}^{LF_{cv}} \sum_{i=1}^M \left(\frac{E_i(t-1) - E_i(t)}{alive(t)} \right), \quad (3)$$

where $alive(t)$ is the number of sensors with a residual energy greater than zero at time $t > 0$ and LF_{cv} is the network lifetime based on the coverage threshold.

- Average Coverage (AC , to maximize): Average coverage provided by the sensors over the network lifetime. There are two main ways to obtain the coverage value in the literature [44]. The first way considers that the coverage provided by a sensor is the area of a circumference of radius R_s . Hence, the coverage provided by all the sensors is the union of the M areas. The second way assumes a $D_x \times D_y$ binary matrix of demand points over the scenario, where only the demand points inside the sensitivity area of an alive sensor take value 1, otherwise 0. Thus, the coverage provided by the network at time t is the percentage of activated demand points at this time. Based on the second way, the fitness function is given by

$$f_2 = LF_{cv}^{-1} \cdot \sum_{t=1}^{LF_{cv}} \sum_{x=1}^{D_x} \sum_{y=1}^{D_y} \left(\frac{R_{xy}(t)}{D_x \cdot D_y} \right), \quad (4)$$

Figure 2. Classical scheme followed by EAs.

Figure 3. Pareto front definition.

where $R(t)$ is the matrix of demand points at time t and $R_{x,y}(t)$ is the demand point placed in the cell (x, y) at such time.

4. EVOLUTIONARY DESIGN

We find several methodologies to solve NP-hard optimization problems in the literature, being EC the most widely considered. This set of problem-solving techniques is based on biological evolution, providing good approximate solutions in reduced computational times.

There are two main techniques in EC: Evolutionary Algorithms (EAs) and algorithms based on swarm intelligence. The first ones are population-based optimization algorithms, which consider mechanisms from Darwin's theory of evolution, such as mutation, crossover, and natural selection. These first algorithms follow a classical scheme (Fig. 2), which starts from a population of random individuals (step 1), where an individual is a possible solution to the optimization problem. Next, the solutions are evaluated according to the fitness functions (step 2). Then, the strongest solutions of the population are selected to be the parents of the next generation (step 3). This new offspring population is generated through reproduction operators in step 4. At this point, if a stop condition is reached, such as a certain number of generations or an elapsed time, the algorithm ends; otherwise, it returns to step 2. On the other hand, swarm intelligence algorithms are based on the behavior of biological systems, such as flocks of birds and ant colonies. In these algorithms, the individuals are modified regarding the overall behavior of all the individuals in the population.

4.1. Multiobjective Optimization and Metaheuristics

There are two main types of optimization problems [8]: SingleOptimization Problems (SOPs), optimizing a single criterion, and MultiObjective Optimization Problems (MOPs), optimizing several criteria. In a general definition, an MOP includes n decision variables, k objective functions, and m constraints. Both objective functions and constraints depend on the decision variables. Thus, an MOP is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{optimize} && y = f(x) = (f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)) \\
 &\text{subject to} && e(x) = (e_1(x), e_2(x), \dots, e_m(x)) \leq 0 \\
 &\text{where} && x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in X \wedge y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k) \in Y,
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where x is the decision vector, y is the objective vector, X is the decision space, and Y is the objective space. The set of all the decision vectors x , which meet the m restrictions is the feasible solution set (X_f) and its image is the feasible region in the objective space (Y_f). The optimization problem consists of finding the $x \in X_f$, providing the best values for $f(x)$. However, in such

Figure 4. Hypervolume metric.

Figure 5. Set coverage metric.

problems, there are not usually a unique solution, but a set of non-dominated solutions, also called Pareto optimal. We say that a solution $x \in X_f$ is Pareto optimal if and only if it is non-dominated, i.e. if there is not any other solution $x' \in X_f$, so that enhances an objective without worsening another. Thus, the Pareto dominance concept (\succ) for a minimization problem is defined as

$$x \succ x' \text{ if } \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}, f_i(x) \leq f_i(x') \wedge \exists j \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\} / f_j(x) < f_j(x'). \quad (6)$$

Accordingly, the set of non-dominated solutions is given by

$$P = \{x \in X_f / \nexists x' \in X_f : x' \succ x\}. \quad (7)$$

The image of this set is known as Pareto front or Pareto frontier, which is the solution set obtained by solving an MOP. Figure 3 shows a Pareto front definition for a minimization problem.

4.2. Chromosome Definition

As stated before, we consider two algorithms belonging to GAs, which is a subclass of EAs. This type of algorithms is characterized by encoding its individuals as chromosomes or arrays [8]. In this work, we assume that a chromosome is a bidimensional coordinate list of M relay nodes, as Fig. 1 shows. Swarm intelligence algorithms do not require to follow any special encoding. However, we consider the same chromosome definition for the three metaheuristics.

4.3. MultiObjective Metrics

Comparing the results obtained through singleobjective algorithms is straightforward, each one provides a unique solution. However, this is not the case for MO algorithms, obtaining sets of non-dominated solutions. With the purpose of solving this issue, we find two main quality metrics in the literature: hypervolume and set coverage.

The hypervolume indicator (I_H) was proposed by Zitzler and Thiele. It calculates the portion of the objective space dominated by a front. Because the objective space could be larger comparing to this portion, we need to delimit it by assuming a pair of reference points called *nadir* and *ideal*. Each one with as many dimensions as objectives the problem has. The *ideal* point dominates all the front values and the *nadir* point is dominated by all of them. Both reference points should be close to the Pareto front, which we analyze to obtain a significant metric. Figure 4 shows a comparison between two fronts, A and B , by assuming the hypervolume. We note that the front A is better than B , because A covers a larger portion of the objective space bounded by the reference points. Accordingly, the hypervolume of A is greater than the provided by B .

The set coverage or coverage relation was proposed by Zitzler. This metric computes the relative spread of solutions between two any Pareto fronts. Thus, $C(A, B)$ calculates the ratio of solutions

Algorithm 1: MO-GSA

Input: $maxT, maxEval, N, M, PS, mProb$ and a clear population R of $2 \cdot PS$ individuals with their velocities ($v_i^d \leftarrow 0, \forall i \in [1, 2 \cdot PS]$ and $\forall d \in [1, M]$)

- 1 /* Generate initial population $R_0 \leftarrow \{X_1, \dots, X_{PS}\}, X_i \leftarrow \{X_i^1, \dots, X_i^M\} \forall i \in [1, PS]$ */
- 2 $R_0 \leftarrow GenerateInitialPopulation(PS)$
- 3 /* Initialize variables */
- 4 $kbest \leftarrow PS, evals \leftarrow 0, it \leftarrow 0$
- 5 /* Define $inT, inkbest$ */
- 6 $inT \leftarrow maxT / (maxEv / (PS + PS \times mProb \times N))$
- 7 $inkbest \leftarrow \lceil (maxEv / ((PS + PS \times mProb \times N))) / kbest \rceil$
- 8 /* Calculate inertia m_i and gravitational M_i masses */
- 9 $m_i \leftarrow (i - worstFitness) / (bestFitness - worstFitness), \forall i \in [1, PS]$
- 10 $M_i \leftarrow \sum_{j=1}^{PS} m_j, \forall i \in [1, PS]$
- 11 **while** $evaluations < maxEval$ **do**
- 12 /* Sort population based on rank and crowding */
- 13 $R_{t+1}, v \leftarrow sortPopulation(R_t)$
- 14 /* Update G_t */
- 15 $G_t \leftarrow 100 \cdot e^{-t}$
- 16 /* Study correspondences among relay nodes */
- 17 $R_{t+1} \leftarrow studyCorrespondences(R_{t+1}, PS)$
- 18 /* Calculate force among masses */
- 19 $F_{ij}^d \leftarrow G \times (M_i \times M_j \times (X_j^d - X_i^d)) / R_{t+1,ij}, \forall i, j \in [1, PS]$ and $\forall d \in [1, M]$
- 20 /* Calculate total force for each mass */
- 21 $F_i^d \leftarrow \sum_{j=1}^{kbest} (F_{i,j}^d \times rand), \forall i \in [1, PS]$ and $\forall d \in [1, M]$
- 22 /* Calculate acceleration a_i^d and velocity v_{PS+i}^d for each mass */
- 23 $a_i^d \leftarrow F_i^d / M_i, \forall i \in [1, PS]$ and $\forall d \in [1, M]$
- 24 $v_{PS+i}^d \leftarrow rand \times v_i^d + a_i^d, \forall i \in [1, PS]$ and $\forall d \in [1, M]$
- 25 /* Calculate new positions X_{PS+i}^d */
- 26 $X_{PS+i}^d \leftarrow X_i^d + v_{PS+i}^d, \forall i \in [1, PS]$ and $\forall d \in [1, M]$ and $evaluateIndividual(X_{PS+i})$
- 27 /* Check stagnation */
- 28 **if** new individuals X_{PS+i}^d do not provide better results than $X_i^d \forall i \in [1, PS]$ and $\forall d \in [1, M]$ **then**
- 29 $X_{PS+i}^d \leftarrow mutateIndividual(X_i^d) \forall i \in [1, PS]$ and $\forall d \in [1, M]$
- 30 **end**
- 31 /* Update variables */
- 32 $t \leftarrow t + inT, it ++$
- 33 **if** $it == inkbest$ **then**
- 34 $kbest --; it \leftarrow 0; inT \leftarrow (maxT - t) / ((maxEv - evals) / (PS + PS \times mProb \times N));$
- 35 $inkbest \leftarrow ((maxEv - evals) / ((PS + PS \times mProb \times N))) / kbest;$
- 36 **end**
- 37 **end**

in the front B , which are weakly dominated by solutions in the front A . This is expressed as

$$C(A, B) = \frac{|\{b \in B / \exists a \in A : a \succeq b\}|}{|B|}. \quad (8)$$

Comparing the fronts in Fig. 5 through this metric, we note that the front A has a set coverage of 80%, and B a value of 20%. Consequently, the front A is better.

5. MULTIOBJECTIVE METAHEURISTICS

As stated before, we consider three different MO algorithms to solve the RNPP. The two standard GAs NSGA-II and SPEA2 were discussed in depth in a prior work [12]. Now, in this section, we describe an MO version of the novel swarm intelligence algorithm GSA.

The original Gravitational Search Algorithm (GSA) was developed by Rashedi et al. This algorithm is considered as an isolated system of masses, where agents are objects and their performances are measured by their masses. All these objects are mutually attracted by the Newtonian laws of gravitation and motion, causing a global movement of all elements towards

heavier masses, which represent the best solutions. Slighter masses move quicker than heavier ones, making easier the exploitation of the solution space. In this work, we propose an MO version of this algorithm by adding some features of NSGA-II to GSA. This is the so-called MO-GSA.

As discussed previously, an individual is composed of M relay nodes. Thus, we define this problem as a set of M independent subsystem of masses, where only the relay nodes performing a similar function can attract each other, i.e. those which are in the same position of the chromosome.

MO-GSA considers a population $R_t = \{X_1, \dots, X_{PS \cdot 2}\}$ divided into two parts of the same size PS , where X_i^d represents the relay node $d \in [1, M]$ of the individual $X_i \in [1, PS \cdot 2]$. At each generation, individuals from the first half (parent population, P_t) are affected by the Newtonian laws, generating new individuals, which are added in the second half (offspring population, Q_t).

As shown in Algorithm 1, P_t is randomly generated and Q_t is empty (line 2). Each individual in P_t has a gravitational mass based on its quality (lines 9-10). This quality value is defined as the position, where an individual is placed after sorting P_t attending to rank and crowding measures, from NSGA-II (line 13). Thus, the best quality value is 0, and the worst one is $PS - 1$ (lines 9, 10).

At each generation, the relay nodes from P_t move due to the forces acting on them (line 26). Being as the position of the relay nodes do not follow any criteria in the chromosome, it is necessary to keep similar relay nodes in the same position for all the individuals. To this end, we follow the next procedure: the best individual of P_t is selected. Then, the relay nodes of the remaining individuals are reorganized attending to the distance to this individual (line 17).

The speed v_i^d $d \in [1, M]$ $i \in [PS, PS \cdot 2]$ of a new agent X_i^d at time t is given by its acceleration a_i^d and its speed in the previous time v_j^d $j = PS - i$ (from the parent population) multiplied by a random number in the interval $[0,1]$ (line 24). This acceleration is due to the total forces acting on the agent divided by its gravitational mass (line 23). These forces are strongly influenced by the gravitational constant G_t (lines 19,21), which is defined by a decreasing function [11] (line 15).

In this decreasing function (G_t), the value of t determines the range of values that the forces take and therefore the movement range of the relay nodes, taking t values from 0 to $maxT$. Moreover, with the purpose of performing a good balance between exploration and exploitation of the solution space, only the *kbest* masses (individuals with better fitness values) act on a mass. This *kbest* value is defined by a decreasing function taking values from PS to 1. In NSGA-II and SPEA2, we consider as stop condition a certain number of evaluations. Being as the number of evaluations performed at each generation is variable, it is important to ensure a proper distribution of both t and *kbest* values during execution time. To this end, both values are adjusted at each generation (lines 6-7 and 33-36).

The stagnation of the algorithm is studied to ensure a good performance (lines 28-30). To this end, we check if the obtained population Q_t provides some improvement over its parent population P_t . If not, we mutate P_t in a similar way as for NSGA-II and SPEA2 to obtain a new P_{t+1} , where all mutated individuals take a speed equal to 0. Finally, only the best PS individuals from $P_t \cup Q_t$ are selected to obtain a new parent population P_{t+1} (line 13).

6. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we discuss the data set assumed and the results obtained by applying the MO metaheuristics, solving such testbed.

6.1. Data Set Definition

With the purpose of comparing among several methodologies solving the RNPP, it is necessary to establish an experimental data set, which is composed of several instances. Each one is a previously-established static traditional WSN, which will be optimized by deploying relay nodes. As stated before, we have not found any public testbed fitting this problem definition. This situation led us to define one, making it available to the scientific community in [15].

We propose two scenarios of 100×100 and 200×200 meters, where a set of sensors and a collector node are placed. The number of sensors assumed in both scenarios is the lower bound of the minimum number of devices to cover the whole surface. Thus, if the area covered by a sensor is $\pi \times R_s^2$ and the area of the scenario is $D_x \times D_y$, it is necessary to deploy $\lceil (D_x \times D_y) / (\pi \times R_s^2) \rceil$

sensors. The collector node is placed on the middle of the surface. The remaining parameters of the RNPP were taken from several papers. We assume $R_c = 30m$ and $R_s = 15m$ from [28]. We also include another $R_c = 60m$ for devices with higher communication capacity. The energy parameters $\alpha=2$, $\beta=1$, $IEC=5J$, and $amp=100pJ/bit/m^2$ were taken from [26]. The information packet size is $128KB$ and the coverage threshold for lifetime is 70%.

A singleobjective GA was assumed to place the sensors in such instances, optimizing the coverage provided by the sensors. For this purpose, the methodology described in Section 3 is considered to obtain the global coverage through a binary matrix of demand points. A threshold value is assumed as stop criterion: if the coverage provided by a solution is greater than 90%, the algorithm ends. The fitness function of this GA is given by

$$\sum_{x=1}^{D_x} \sum_{y=1}^{D_y} \left(\frac{R_{x,y}}{D_x \times D_y} \right), \quad (9)$$

where R is the matrix of demand points and $R_{x,y}$ is the demand point placed in the cell (x, y) of R .

As result, four different instances were generated, which are described in Table I. The name of the instances follow the notation $D_x \times D_y - R_s - R_c$. Note that we also include the fitness values of the RNPP without considering relay nodes, these values are *HO-AEC* and *HO-AC*.

6.2. Experimental Results

The inclusion of relay nodes involves an economic cost. Hence, we decided not to include more than a 20% of these devices, regarding the number of sensors deployed. Therefore, as Table II describes, we define 12 different test cases, assuming the notation *instance(number of relay nodes)*.

A same population size and stop criteria are considered for all the algorithms to be fair in the comparisons. The population size is fixed to 100 individuals. The stop criteria are 50 000, 100 000, 200 000, 300 000, and 400 000 evaluations. These values were selected experimentally, being enough to get good solutions and sufficiently spaced to analyze the convergence of the algorithms.

Before performing the executions, the algorithms must be adjusted. The parameters of NSGA-II and SPEA2 are mutation and crossover probabilities. For MO-GSA, it is the mutation probability. The procedure is as follows: we start from a default configuration, fixing the parameters one by one in their optimal values through a parametric sweep [45]. Thus, the parameters of NSGA-II and SPEA2 take a same value of 0.5 and the parameter of MO-GSA assumes a value of 0.4.

Table II shows hypervolume and standard deviation for each test case, algorithm, and stop condition, being the average value of 31 independent runs (30 runs is a quite typical number [46]). As stated before, we need to define a pair of reference points to calculate the hypervolume metric. These values were fixed by studying the extreme points of the Pareto fronts obtained. They appear in Table II. When we work with average values, an important step is to decide which we must consider: the mean or the median. For this purpose, we propose the following statistical hypothesis: H_0 if data come from a normal distribution and H_1 if data do not come from a normal distribution, solving it through Shapiro–Wilk’s [47] and Kolmogorov–Smirnov–Lilliefors’s [48] tests. We obtained p-values lower to 0.05 for all the cases. This means that we cannot assume that data come from a Gaussian distribution. Accordingly, we consider the mean (*Me*) as average value. Note that before this statistical study, we remove all the possible outliers from samples.

Analyzing Table II, MO-GSA seems to provide a better behavior. If we focus on 400 000 evaluations, this fact is increased as Fig. 6 shows. However, we do not know if this behavior is significant. To this end, we propose the following hypothesis H_0 if $Me_1 = Me_2 = Me_3$ and H_1 if at least two of them are different. To simplify the notation, the algorithm 1 is MO-GSA, 2 is NSGA-II, and 3 is SPEA2. As we cannot assume a normal distribution and samples are independent, we consider the Kruskal–Wallis’s test [49]. As result, we obtained p-values lower than 0.05 for all the cases. Therefore, there are significant differences between at least two of the algorithms.

The next step is to study these differences, defining hypotheses H_0 if $Me_i \leq Me_j$ and H_1 if $Me_i > Me_j$, with $i = 1, 2, 3$, $j = 2, 3$, and $i < j$. The notation considered is the same as in the previous test. As data do not come from a normal distribution and samples are independent, we

Figure 6. Comparing median hypervolumes for 400 000 evaluations.

consider the Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney’s test [50]. The p-values obtained are shown in Table III. If we observe the p-values of MO-GSA vs NSGA-II, we note some values greater than 0.05. However, when the number of evaluations increases, this situation disappears and MO-GSA becomes the clear winner. Analyzing the comparative between NSGA-II and SPEA2, we have a similar situation due to the convergence speed of the algorithms, being NSGA-II better than SPEA2. Finally, MO-GSA is clearly better than SPEA2 in the last test. In conclusion, we can affirm that the differences among the hypervolumes shown in Table II and Fig. 6 are significant. This way, we define a quality order based on the hypervolume metric: MO-GSA > NSGA-II > SPEA2.

We also consider the set coverage metric. Table IV shows the coverage relation among the median fronts obtained for 400 000 evaluations. These fronts are shown in Fig. 7 and 8. In some cases, the interpretation of these plots is not easy, because the number of points is high and sometimes the algorithms find the same solutions. Analyzing such figures, we note a similar behavior as described by the hypervolume indicator. In Table IV, we check that MO-GSA widely dominates the other algorithms with an average value of 81.65%. Equally, NSGA-II widely dominates SPEA2, but almost nothing to MO-GSA, having an average value of 52.47%. Finally, SPEA2 has the lowest coverage value with 29.35%. We observe a shocking case for the instance 200x200_15_30(9), the coverage relation of MO-GSA is low. However, the average hypervolume of MO-GSA is the highest for such test case, implying that MO-GSA explores a different area of the solution space.

Up to this point, we have analyzed the quality of the results obtained through MO metrics. Now, we study the advantages, which accrue from adding relay nodes to previously-established static WSNS. To this end, we consider the results obtained through MO-GSA, because this is the algorithm providing the best behavior. Table VI shows *AEC* and *AC* for each test case. These values are the extreme points of the median Pareto fronts for 400 000 evaluations (Fig. 7 and Fig. 8). If we compare these results to the values shown in Table I for these test cases without assuming relay nodes, we note that the energy consumption is considerably decreased. Figures 9 and 10 show lifetime-coverage relation and the distribution of the energy consumption in the surface, where a warm color implies a high consumption and a cool color the opposite. Figure 9 assumes the instances without including relay nodes and Fig. 10 considers a extreme solution of each test case assuming the highest number of relay nodes. Thus, we check that deploying relay nodes implies a great decrease of the energy consumption, distributing in a more efficient way the energy cost, while the average coverage is maximized during lifetime. With the goal of detailing a full solution of the RNPP, Fig. 11 shows a solution obtained by MO-GSA for 200x200_15_60(9), assuming 400 000 evaluations. This is the median solution of the median Pareto front from the distribution of 31 samples.

In terms of optimality, it will be useful to check if MO-GSA is able to provide optimal solutions if the number of evaluations is sufficiently increased. To this end, instead of greatly increasing the number of evaluations, we assume a small instance 30x30_15_30, where we include two sensors and a collector node. Next, the algorithm studies how to deploy an additional relay node, considering 400 000 evaluations. With the purpose of checking if the Pareto front obtained is the optimal Pareto

Figure 7. Comparing median Pareto fronts obtained by NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-GSA. (a) $100 \times 100_{15_30}(2)$ (b) $100 \times 100_{15_30}(3)$ (c) $100 \times 100_{15_60}(2)$ (d) $100 \times 100_{15_60}(3)$ (e) $200 \times 200_{15_30}(2)$ (f) $200 \times 200_{15_30}(4)$.

front, we consider an exhaustive search, generating all the possible solutions with a resolution of 0.00625 meters, i.e. 23 040 000 solutions were generated. Analysing the results obtained by the two approaches, we reach the same non-dominated solutions. Hence, MO-GSA is able to find the optimal Pareto front in reduced instances. More details appear in Table V.

Finally, some implementation details. Both the problem definition and the algorithms were programmed by ourselves in C++, using the Lemon library for graphs (<http://lemon.cs.elte.hu>). Wilcoxon - Mann-Whitney's and Kruskal - Wallis's tests were taken from [51], and Shapiro - Wilk's and Kolmogrov - Smirnov - Lilliefors's tests were taken from the IBM SPSS software.

Figure 8. Comparing median Pareto fronts obtained by NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-GSA. (a) $200 \times 200_{15_30}(6)$ (b) $200 \times 200_{15_30}(9)$ (c) $200 \times 200_{15_60}(2)$ (d) $200 \times 200_{15_60}(4)$ (e) $200 \times 200_{15_60}(6)$ (f) $200 \times 200_{15_60}(9)$.

7. COMPARISONS WITH OTHER AUTHOR APPROACHES

As discussed before, we have not found any work in the literature, providing a free-access data set, which fit this problem definition. Hence, we cannot compare our results to other approaches. Analyzing related work in Section 2, most papers assume such limitation.

With the purpose of mitigating such deficiency, a paper with a similar approach was selected from the current literature. In [31], Hou et al. proposed a heuristic to optimize the network lifetime by adding relay nodes to previously established two-tiered WSNs. Following this model, a two-tiered WSN is composed of some clusters and a Base Station (BS). Each cluster consists of a number of MicroSensor Nodes (MSNs) and one Aggregation and Forwarding Node (AFN). MSNs capture information, which is transmitted to the local AFN via single-hop transmission. Then, the local AFN relays all this information to the BS via single or multi-hop transmission. Finally, RNs are additional devices, which only relay all the received information from AFNs to the BS. In this WSN definition

Figure 9. Energy distribution and lifetime-coverage plots for each instance without deploying relay nodes.
 (a) $100 \times 100_{15_30}$ (b) $100 \times 100_{15_60}$ (c) $200 \times 200_{15_30}$ (d) $200 \times 200_{15_60}$.

all the devices, excepting the BS, are powered by batteries. Hence, they are conditioned to energy constraints. In addition, the devices can have different initial energy charges.

We assumed the SPINDS heuristic proposed in [31] to optimize our data set. As both network models are different, we implemented the algorithm assuming some assumptions: 1) MSNs are not included. Now, AFNs are equivalent to sensor nodes in our model. 2) The amount of information sent by an AFN depends on the number of MSNs in its cluster. As now MSNs are not included, all AFNs have to send an information packet of size K per time unit. 3) RNs are not powered by batteries, and the initial energy charge of AFNs is a fixed value given by the parameter IEC . 4) The lifetime criterion in [31] is different from our approach: they defined the network lifetime as the time when any of the AFNs failed. Now, the lifetime criterion is based on the coverage threshold. 5) Finally, the energy model assumed is the described in this paper.

Table VI shows the results obtained by SPINDS. Studying this table, we note that MO-GSA is an MO algorithm, which optimizes both average coverage and average energy consumption, whereas SPINDS is a singleobjective algorithm, optimizing the network lifetime. Thus, MO-GSA provides a

Figure 10. Energy distribution and lifetime-coverage plots for each instance, assuming MO-GSA and the highest number of relay nodes. (a) 100x100_15_30 (b) 100x100_15_60 (c) 200x200_15_30 (d) 200x200_15_60.

Relay node placement		
id	x	y
#1	29.1078	168.6705
#2	87.9769	155.7788
#3	171.3900	42.1625
#4	158.9540	114.8837
#5	43.3109	102.8142
#6	79.2938	34.7408
#7	26.9950	47.6788
#8	163.2953	174.8821
#9	124.9714	34.9991

Fitness functions	
AEC	0.0613
AC	86.78%

Figure 11. A solution obtained by MO-GSA for 200x200_15_60(9).

set of non-dominated solutions and SPINDS provides a unique solution. As we check, the solutions provided by MO-GSA dominate all the solutions of SPINDS, but $200 \times 200_{15.60(2)}$, providing SPINDS a non-dominated solution. This comparison allows validating our proposal, giving an idea of the complexity of the data set.

Table VII shows average execution times for NSGA-II, SPEA2, MO-GSA, and SPINDS. We note that the three algorithms from EC need similar times for 400 000 evaluations, i.e. most of the execution time is assumed to calculate the fitness functions. Thus, MO-GSA outperforms the other three EC algorithms without needing additional time. Comparing to SPINDS, EC algorithms need a greater execution time than the heuristic. However, they are able to provide approximate good solutions in a reasonable computing time, as discussed previously in Table VI.

8. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, we study how to deploy relay nodes in previously-established static WSNs, with the goal of optimizing two important factors: average energy consumption and average coverage. This is the so-called RNPP, which is an NP-hard optimization problem. Hence, exact techniques are discarded. Thus, we consider three MO algorithms from EC. Two of them are well-known GAs, which offer good solutions in many optimization problems, NSGA-II and SPEA2, and the third is an MO version of a new swarm intelligence algorithm based on gravitational forces, MO-GSA.

Because we did not find any data set fitting this problem definition, we defined one, making it available to the scientific community. This data set is composed of some traditional WSNs, where a collector node and several sensors are deployed. The number of sensors assumed is the lower bound of the minimum number of devices to cover the whole surface. Then, we apply the algorithms to optimize the data set, taking into account that the number of relay nodes must be considerably lower than the number of sensors. The results obtained are quantified through two relevant MO metric: hypervolume and set coverage. After a careful statistical analysis, we note that MO-GSA provides the best results by solving the data set, followed by NSGA-II and SPEA2 in the tail.

From the solutions provided by MO-GSA, we study the advantages, which accrue from adding relay nodes to the experimental instances. For this purpose, we compare average energy consumption and average coverage obtained for all the test cases with and without deploying relay nodes. Concluding that the addition of relay nodes is a good choice to optimize a WSN, efficiently distributing the energy consumption and positively affecting the coverage provided. Finally, this methodology is validated by comparing our work to another author approach from the literature, checking as our proposal provides good solutions solving the data set.

As future work, we could consider more complex instances from the real world and other MO algorithms. Moreover, it could be interesting to adopt more realistic communication and energy models. To this end, we could include new features from a WSN simulator, such as Castalia [52], which is based on OMNeT++ platform [53]. This type of network simulator cannot be directly assumed following this problem definition, because they do not include important concepts, such as coverage and network lifetime. Another great extension of this work could be that the optimization process provides the number of relay nodes needed attending to some thresholds, such as energy and coverage, i.e. the number of relay nodes deployed could be another objective of the MO problem.

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REFERENCES

1. Mukherjee JYB, Ghosal D. Wireless sensor network survey. *Computer Networks* 2008; **52**:2292–2330.
2. Chowdhury IFATMKR. A survey on wireless multimedia sensor networks. *Computer Networks* 2007; **51**(4):921–960.

3. Xu K, Hassanein H, Takahara G, Wang Q. Relay node deployment strategies in heterogeneous wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing* 2010; **9**:145–159.
4. Lloyd EL, Xue G. Relay node placement in wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Computers* 2007; **56**:134–138.
5. Garey MR, Johnson DS. *Computers and Intractability: A Guide to the Theory of NP-Completeness*. W. H. Freeman & Co., 1979.
6. Cheng X, Narahari B, Simha R, Cheng M, Liu D. Strong minimum energy topology in wireless sensor networks: Np-completeness and heuristics. *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing* 2003; **2**:248–256.
7. Clementi AEF, Penna P, Silvestri R. Hardness results for the power range assignment problem in packet radio networks. *Proceedings of RANDOM-APPROX*, vol. 1671, 1999; 197–208.
8. Zitzler E. *Evolutionary Algorithms for Multiobjective Optimization: Methods and Applications*. (Doctoral dissertation). Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH), 1999.
9. Deb K, Pratap A, Agarwal S, Meyarivan T. A fast elitist multi-objective genetic algorithm: Nsga-ii. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 2000; **6**:182–197.
10. Zitzler E, Laumanns M, Thiele L. Spea2: Improving the strength pareto evolutionary algorithm. *Technical Report*, Computer Engineering and Networks Laboratory (TIK), ETH Zurich 2001.
11. Rashedi E, Nezamabadi-pour H, Saryazdi S. Gsa: A gravitational search algorithm. *Information Sciences* 2009; **179**:2232–2248.
12. Lanza-Gutierrez JM, Gomez-Pulido JA, Vega-Rodriguez MA, Sanchez-Perez JM. Relay node positioning in wireless sensor networks by means of evolutionary techniques. *Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 7326. Springer Berlin / Heidelberg, 2012; 18–25.
13. Lanza-Gutierrez JM, Gomez-Pulido JA, Vega-Rodriguez MA, Sanchez-Perez JM. A parallel evolutionary approach to solve the relay node placement problem in wireless sensor networks. *Proceeding of GECCO*, 2013; 1157–1164.
14. Knowles J, Thiele L, Zitzler E. A tutorial on the performance assessment of stochastic multiobjective optimizers. *Technical Report*, Computer Engineering and Networks Laboratory (TIK), ETH Zurich, Switzerland 2006.
15. Lanza-Gutierrez JM, Gomez-Pulido JA, Vega-Rodriguez MA, Sanchez-Perez JM. Instance sets for optimization in wireless sensor networks. <http://arco.unex.es/wsnopt> 2011.
16. Deif DS, Gadallah Y. Classification of wireless sensor networks deployment techniques. *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials* 2014; **16**:834–855.
17. Chang JH, Tassiulas L. Maximum lifetime routing in wireless sensor networks. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking* 2004; **12**:609–619.
18. Cardei M, Du DZ. Improving wireless sensor network lifetime through power aware organization. *Wireless Networks* 2005; **11**:333–340.
19. Zhang H, Hou J. Maintaining sensing coverage and connectivity in large sensor networks. *Ad Hoc & Sensor Wireless Networks* 2005; **1**:89–124.
20. Liu L, Hu B, Li L. Energy conservation algorithms for maintaining coverage and connectivity in wireless sensor networks. *IET Communications* 2010; **4**:786–800.
21. Mahboubi H, Moezzi K, Aghdam A, Sayrafian-Pour K, Marbukh V. Distributed deployment algorithms for improved coverage in a network of wireless mobile sensors. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 2014; **10**:163–174.
22. Konstantinidis A, Yang K, Zhang Q. An evolutionary algorithm to a multi-objective deployment and power assignment problem in wireless sensor networks. *Proceedings of IEEE GLOBECOM*, 2008; 1–6.
23. Jia J, Chen J, Chang G, Tan Z. Energy efficient coverage control in wireless sensor networks based on multi-objective genetic algorithm. *Computers and Mathematics with Applications* 2009; **57**:1756–1766.
24. Jia J, Chen J, Chang G, Wen Y, Song J. Multi-objective optimization for coverage control in wireless sensor network with adjustable sensing radius. *Computers and Mathematics with Applications* 2009; **57**:1767–1775.
25. Hu XM, Zhang J, Yu Y, Chung HH, Li YL, Shi YH, Luo XN. Hybrid genetic algorithm using a forward encoding scheme for lifetime maximization of wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 2010; **14**:766–781.
26. Konstantinidis A, Yang K. Multi-objective k-connected deployment and power assignment in wsns using a problem-specific constrained evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition. *Computer Communications* 2011; **34**:83–98.
27. Le Berre M, Hnaïen F, Snoussi H. Multi-objective optimization in wireless sensors networks. *Proceedings of ICM*, vol. 1, 2011; 1–4.
28. Martins F, Carrano E, Wanner E, Takahashi R, Mateus G. A hybrid multiobjective evolutionary approach for improving the performance of wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Sensors Journal* 2011; **11**:545–554.
29. Yoon Y, Kim YH. An efficient genetic algorithm for maximum coverage deployment in wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics* 2013; **43**:1473–1483.
30. Mini S, Udgata S, Sabat S. Sensor deployment and scheduling for target coverage problem in wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Sensors Journal* 2014; **14**:636–644.
31. Hou Y, Shi Y, Sherali H, Midkiff S. On energy provisioning and relay node placement for wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications* 2005; **4**:2579–2590.
32. Tang J, Hao B, Sen A. Relay node placement in large scale wireless sensor networks. *Computer Communications* 2006; **29**:490–501.
33. Wang Q, Xu K, Takahara G, Hassanein H. Device placement for heterogeneous wireless sensor networks: Minimum cost with lifetime constraints. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications* 2007; **6**:2444–2453.
34. Lloyd EL, Xue G. Relay node placement in wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Computers* 2007; **56**:134–138.
35. Han X, Cao X, Lloyd EL, Shen CC. Fault-tolerant relay node placement in heterogeneous wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing* 2010; **9**:643–656.
36. Misra S, Majd N, Huang H. Constrained relay node placement in energy harvesting wireless sensor networks. *Proceedings of IEEE MASS*, vol. 1, 2011; 25–34.

37. Misra S, Majd NE, Huang H. Approximation algorithms for constrained relay node placement in energy harvesting wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Computers* 2013; **99**:PrePrints.
38. Nigam A, Agarwal YK. Optimal relay node placement in delay constrained wireless sensor network design. *European Journal of Operational Research* 2014; **233**:220–233.
39. Zhao C, Chen P. Particle swarm optimization for optimal deployment of relay nodes in hybrid sensor networks. *Proceedings of IEEE CEC*, vol. 1, 2007; 3316–3320.
40. Perez A, Labrador M, Wightman P. A multiobjective approach to the relay placement problem in wsns. *Proceedings of IEEE WCNC*, vol. 1, 2011; 475–480.
41. Peiravi A, Mashhadi HR, Hamed Javadi S. An optimal energy-efficient clustering method in wireless sensor networks using multi-objective genetic algorithm. *International Journal of Communication Systems* 2013; **26**:114–126.
42. Cormen TH, Leiserson CE, Rivest RL, Stein C. *Introduction to Algorithms(Third Edition)*. The MIT Press, 2009.
43. Ye W, Heidemann J, Estrin D. An energy-efficient mac protocol for wireless sensor networks. *Proceedings of INFOCOM*, vol. 3, 2002; 1567–1576.
44. Wang B. Coverage problems in sensor networks: A survey. *ACM Computing Surveys* 2011; **43**:32:1–32:53.
45. Lanza-Gutierrez JM, Gomez-Pulido JA, Vega-Rodriguez MA, Sanchez-Perez JM. A multi-objective network design for real traffic models of the internet by means of a parallel framework for solving np-hard problems. *NABIC*, 2011; 137–142.
46. Hays W, Winkler R. *Statistics: probability, inference, and decision*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston, 1970.
47. Shapiro SS, Wilk MB. An analysis of variance test for normality (complete samples). *Biometrika* 1965; **52**:591–611.
48. Lilliefors HW. On the kolmogorov-smirnov test for normality with mean and variance unknown. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 1967; **62**:399–402.
49. Kruskal WH, Wallis WA. Use of Ranks in One-Criterion Variance Analysis. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 1952; **47**:583–621.
50. Mann HB, Whitney DR. On a test of whether one of two random variables is stochastically larger than the other. *Annals of Mathematical Statistics* 1947; **1**:50–60.
51. Fonseca C, Knowles J, Thiele L, Zitzler E. Performance assessment tool suite. <http://www.tik.ee.ethz.ch/pisa/?page=assessment.php>.
52. Castalia: Wireless sensor network simulator. <https://castalia.forge.nicta.com.au/index.php/en/>.
53. Omnet++ network simulation framework. <http://www.omnetpp.org>.

Table I. Instances considered in this work.

Instance	$D_x \times D_y$	M	R_c	HO-AEC	HO-AC	Ref AEC		Ref AC	
						ideal	nadir	ideal	nadir
100x100_15_30	100x100	15	30	0.1091	89.24%	0.02	0.1	100%	60%
100x100_15_60	100x100	15	60	0.1482	86.63%	0.02	0.1	100%	60%
200x200_15_30	200x200	57	30	0.2791	87.10%	0.10	0.30	100%	60%
200x200_15_60	200x200	57	60	0.3871	82.43%	0.10	0.30	100%	60%

Table II. Hypervolumes and standard deviation following the notation $hypervolume_{deviation}$.

	NSGA-II				
	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100_15_30(2)	42.40% 0.0029	42.45% 0.0030	42.67% 0.0002	42.69% 0.0002	42.69% 0.0002
100x100_15_30(3)	55.02% 0.0044	55.37% 0.0023	55.53% 0.0027	55.55% 0.0024	55.66% 0.0004
100x100_15_60(2)	31.60% 0.0019	31.80% 0.0012	31.82% 0.0014	31.86% 0.0010	31.94% 0.0000
100x100_15_60(3)	58.97% 0.0035	59.25% 0.0035	59.69% 0.0019	59.73% 0.0022	59.91% 0.0016
200x200_15_30(2)	34.39% 0.0193	35.39% 0.0175	36.33% 0.0152	37.06% 0.0103	37.42% 0.0050
200x200_15_30(4)	43.41% 0.0435	44.46% 0.0454	46.45% 0.0509	47.22% 0.0519	47.48% 0.0537
200x200_15_30(6)	53.70% 0.0792	59.27% 0.0643	64.61% 0.0087	65.01% 0.0094	65.26% 0.0110
200x200_15_30(9)	73.67% 0.0173	76.16% 0.0114	77.56% 0.0117	78.14% 0.0117	78.47% 0.0109
200x200_15_60(2)	23.40% 0.0048	23.92% 0.0046	23.93% 0.0037	23.94% 0.0028	24.00% 0.0032
200x200_15_60(4)	58.16% 0.0086	58.72% 0.0070	59.94% 0.0056	60.08% 0.0046	60.15% 0.0045
200x200_15_60(6)	71.79% 0.0098	74.11% 0.0076	75.42% 0.0093	75.93% 0.0103	76.37% 0.0096
200x200_15_60(9)	85.98% 0.0105	88.38% 0.0086	90.05% 0.0074	90.51% 0.0079	90.94% 0.0079
	SPEA2				
	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100_15_30(2)	42.11% 0.0036	42.45% 0.0028	42.65% 0.0004	42.66% 0.0002	42.66% 0.0001
100x100_15_30(3)	53.71% 0.0085	53.78% 0.0080	53.94% 0.0072	54.24% 0.0067	53.87% 0.0065
100x100_15_60(2)	31.35% 0.0027	31.57% 0.0018	31.78% 0.0014	31.82% 0.0012	31.87% 0.0008
100x100_15_60(3)	57.96% 0.0068	58.63% 0.0056	58.97% 0.0078	58.84% 0.0072	59.36% 0.0041
200x200_15_30(2)	34.08% 0.0139	34.35% 0.0137	34.72% 0.0140	34.85% 0.0113	34.99% 0.0109
200x200_15_30(4)	44.14% 0.0328	44.71% 0.0383	45.31% 0.0382	45.49% 0.0385	45.63% 0.0385
200x200_15_30(6)	57.93% 0.0139	61.62% 0.0160	63.22% 0.0188	63.80% 0.0164	64.07% 0.0165
200x200_15_30(9)	70.79% 0.0075	74.49% 0.0101	75.63% 0.0106	75.97% 0.0118	76.35% 0.0111
200x200_15_60(2)	22.91% 0.0036	23.29% 0.0036	23.65% 0.0030	23.81% 0.0024	23.94% 0.0017
200x200_15_60(4)	57.43% 0.0074	58.57% 0.0061	59.30% 0.0043	59.74% 0.0051	59.98% 0.0033
200x200_15_60(6)	71.24% 0.0067	72.69% 0.0060	73.59% 0.0076	74.04% 0.0087	74.35% 0.0112
200x200_15_60(9)	84.22% 0.0050	86.45% 0.0037	88.19% 0.0096	89.27% 0.0102	89.71% 0.0102
	MO-GSA				
	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100_15_30(2)	43.79% 0.0050	44.01% 0.0034	44.17% 0.0028	44.28% 0.0014	44.26% 0.0008
100x100_15_30(3)	56.09% 0.0075	56.73% 0.0065	57.23% 0.0041	57.40% 0.0040	57.57% 0.0030
100x100_15_60(2)	33.24% 0.0060	33.52% 0.0055	33.72% 0.0032	33.78% 0.0033	33.80% 0.0034
100x100_15_60(3)	60.56% 0.0049	60.87% 0.0055	61.13% 0.0042	61.26% 0.0037	61.33% 0.0032
200x200_15_30(2)	36.81% 0.0136	37.53% 0.0098	38.00% 0.0073	38.23% 0.0077	38.47% 0.0063
200x200_15_30(4)	49.03% 0.0225	50.34% 0.0222	51.12% 0.0188	51.53% 0.0178	52.02% 0.0171
200x200_15_30(6)	63.79% 0.0185	65.03% 0.0144	65.90% 0.0122	66.16% 0.0131	66.44% 0.0121
200x200_15_30(9)	75.01% 0.0150	76.54% 0.0145	77.85% 0.0136	78.47% 0.0125	78.97% 0.0101
200x200_15_60(2)	23.29% 0.0068	23.69% 0.0045	23.94% 0.0050	24.02% 0.0045	24.12% 0.0040
200x200_15_60(4)	60.44% 0.0068	60.74% 0.0057	61.02% 0.0044	61.16% 0.0035	61.29% 0.0036
200x200_15_60(6)	74.11% 0.0103	75.29% 0.0074	76.08% 0.0080	76.59% 0.0076	76.92% 0.0088
200x200_15_60(9)	88.46% 0.0067	89.85% 0.0050	90.73% 0.0078	91.19% 0.0079	91.45% 0.0085

Table III. P-values comparing the algorithms through the hypervolume metric.

	MO-GSA vs NSGA-II					NSGA-II vs SPEA2				
	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100_15_30(2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.1520	0.0027	0.0000	0.0000
100x100_15_30(3)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
100x100_15_60(2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0001	0.0000	0.0466	0.0163	0.0000
100x100_15_60(3)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_30(2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.2014	0.0034	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_30(4)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0001	0.0004	0.0005	0.9235	0.7157	0.2138	0.0388	0.0106
200x200_15_30(6)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0001	0.0007	0.0006	0.8080	0.2904	0.0008	0.0017	0.0018
200x200_15_30(9)	0.0023	0.2180	0.1782	0.1227	0.0436	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_60(2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0075	0.0045	0.0075	0.0015	0.0009
200x200_15_60(4)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0075	0.0005	0.0001	0.0002	0.0001
200x200_15_60(6)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0019	0.0077	0.0202	0.0075	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_60(9)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0005	0.0006	0.0053	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

MO-GSA vs SPEA2					
	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100_15_30(2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
100x100_15_30(3)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
100x100_15_60(2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
100x100_15_60(3)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_30(2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_30(4)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_30(6)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_30(9)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_60(2)	0.0021	0.0004	0.0080	0.0036	0.0035
200x200_15_60(4)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_60(6)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
200x200_15_60(9)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Table IV. Coverage relation among the algorithms C(A,B) for 400 000 evaluations.

	A	MO-GSA		NSGA-II		SPEA2	
		NSGA-II	SPEA2	MO-GSA	SPEA2	MO-GSA	NSGA-2
100x100_15_30(2)		94.59%	82.46%	0.00%	96.49%	0.00%	72.97%
100x100_15_30(3)		91.22%	100.00%	48.89%	100.00%	9.40%	50.50%
100x100_15_60(2)		96.60%	100.00%	6.52%	91.87%	6.77%	80.80%
100x100_15_60(3)		100.00%	100.00%	0.00%	74.60%	0.00%	39.80%
200x200_15_30(2)		85.79%	99.68%	95.48%	100.00%	90.32%	20.81%
200x200_15_30(4)		98.09%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%
200x200_15_30(6)		96.63%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%
200x200_15_30(9)		0.00%	0.07%	73.95%	100.00%	31.17%	0.00%
200x200_15_60(2)		84.78%	81.82%	28.57%	54.55%	35.71%	67.39%
200x200_15_60(4)		88.24%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	8.33%	47.06%
200x200_15_60(6)		80.37%	50.65%	0.00%	28.57%	71.20%	41.12%
200x200_15_60(9)		92.86%	85.71%	59.71%	100.00%	30.94%	0.00%
Partial average		84.10%	79.20%	26.09%	78.84%	23.65%	35.04%
Average		81.65%		52.47%		29.35%	

Table V. Optimal solutions for 30x30_15_30.

Device placement		
	x	y
collector	15.00	15.00
sensor#1	15.00	20.00
sensor#2	5.00	12.00

Optimal solutions		
	AEC	AC
solution#1	0.0013	92.87%
solution#2	0.0027	92.88%

Table VI. Comparing between extreme values of MO-GSA for 400 000 evaluations and SPINDS algorithm.

	MO-GSA Extreme 1		MO-GSA Extreme 2		SPINDS	
	AEC	AC	AEC	AC	AEC	AC
100x100_15_30(2)	0.0549	89.52%	0.0613	91.53%	0.0610	89.46%
100x100_15_30(3)	0.0414	89.53%	0.0622	91.56%	0.0534	88.80%
100x100_15_60(2)	0.0629	82.09%	0.0877	91.26%	0.0642	82.09%
100x100_15_60(3)	0.0344	78.61%	0.0639	91.45%	0.0492	83.16%
200x200_15_30(2)	0.1925	86.83%	0.2589	88.84%	0.2655	86.45%
200x200_15_30(4)	0.1585	89.08%	0.1686	89.51%	0.1851	86.22%
200x200_15_30(6)	0.1266	90.60%	0.1336	90.83%	0.1653	85.68%
200x200_15_30(9)	0.1000	90.05%	0.0998	90.05%	0.1171	86.15%
200x200_15_60(2)	0.2944	84.75%	0.2584	87.52%	0.2545	83.33%
200x200_15_60(4)	0.1364	87.47%	0.1496	90.02%	0.1598	86.75%
200x200_15_60(6)	0.1001	89.18%	0.0991	89.00%	0.1108	84.88%
200x200_15_60(9)	0.1048	90.19%	0.0713	90.01%	0.0716	82.04%

Table VII. Average execution times in seconds.

	<i>NSGA-II</i>	<i>SPEA2</i>	<i>MO-GSA</i>	<i>SPINDS</i>
100x100_15_30(2)	15100	12800	12200	4
100x100_15_30(3)	16300	14400	14600	8
100x100_15_60(2)	8370	8380	11000	4
100x100_15_60(3)	13100	15500	18200	6
200x200_15_30(2)	13200	12000	9760	45
200x200_15_30(4)	15000	17700	16200	150
200x200_15_30(6)	19300	17900	17800	270
200x200_15_30(9)	24000	21100	20100	479
200x200_15_60(2)	15200	15400	14600	91
200x200_15_60(4)	21500	22500	21500	466
200x200_15_60(6)	25200	24100	28000	436
200x200_15_60(9)	37700	39300	37700	1020